

Open Source Secure Data Infrastructure and Processes for Data Visiting

Technical Report

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Abstract

Meeting the conflicting goals of protecting and maintaining control over sensitive data while also allowing access by third parties constitutes a significant challenge. Secure data infrastructures support data visiting in a highly controlled and monitored environment which, if properly set-up and operated, provide high security guarantees through a combination of technical, legal and procedural mechanisms.

To ease the process of deploying such a secure data infrastructure, we present a detailed documentation of the architecture and processes of such an infrastructure and provide a pre-configured reference implementation based entirely on open source software that can be flexibly configured to meet differing security requirements and deployment scenarios.

We combine mechanisms for data visiting on secured infrastructure components with optional components of data anonymization and fingerprinting, covered by extensive logging and monitoring functions and embedded in defined processes and contractual frameworks based upon the experience of operating such a secure infrastructure in the medical domain for almost ten years, addressing the emerging need to make such a solution available to a larger set of stakeholders.

We show that our system significantly enhances data visiting, offers a higher level of isolation and present lessons learned.

1 Introduction

In an increasing number of settings we face the need to safeguard access to highly sensitive data, e.g. due to privacy requirements or commercial sensitivity of data, while still wanting to make it accessible to third parties for research purposes or to assist with specific analytical tasks. This challenge has become acute during the early days of the COVID-19 pandemic when evidence-based decision making required the analysis and sometimes integration of highly sensitive (due to privacy or commercial reasons) information such as health data, social science data, movement data from telecom operators as well as supply-chain logistics data from the retail

sector. But even outside this exceptional situation, academia-industry collaborations as well as industry-to-industry co-operations frequently are hindered by the conflicting needs to keep the data that the other party should process or analyze secret. Homomorphic encryption, while ensuring that the data is kept hidden from the analyst, does not sufficiently support the exploratory and interactive types of analyses required in many settings, which frequently require an analyst to actually see the data and interpret instance-level characteristics and attribute semantics.

While data sharing is being proclaimed as the future in open science, many settings do not allow for such approaches. Data visiting, on the other hand, is an approach where data stays under the control of the owner and allows the consumers (e.g. analysts or machine learning algorithms) to come to the data to work with it. Closely monitoring the processes and interaction with data during these visits allows to put a certain level of safe-guards in place to prevent accidental data leakage or intentional data breaches. However, most research infrastructures provide data visiting support only on a very rudimentary level, sometimes even failing to prevent the (even unintended) export of parts of data via simple file transfer mechanisms when analysis results containing parts of the data are downloaded.

We define and document a system architecture and provide a modular pre-packaged configuration of components constituting the core of such a secure data infrastructure as reference implementation. Selecting only open source, well-known and tested components allows us to minimize risks of data-theft while at the same time focusing on the main research challenge: design a secure system and identifying compulsory and optional components, as well as processes needed to operate it. Contractual obligations that need to be defined are discussed as part of the infrastructure set-up to complement the technical measures. It is initially configured to run as a trusted third-party environment, with a subset of this configuration being suitable for deployment within a data owner's environment. It is the result of a second iteration of the initial, handcrafted solution using the experience gathered

of the set-up and operation of a trusted third party data platform as joint initiative of our institutional IT operations, a national research center on IT security and technical expertise of the people involved, findings of internal audits and user feedback. This paper presents the architecture of the resulting secure data infrastructure, discusses design decisions and touches upon the processes complementing the system set-up. Additionally, it presents a condensed summary of the risk factors involved and omitted and ideas for modular additions to enhance the level of security in the system. On the contrary, we do not cover general aspects of IT infrastructure security or preventing brute-force attacks on the system, but rather focus on avoiding data leakage occurring most likely from ignorance and accidental disclosure. We argue the latter as experience where in a decade, no adversary tried to steal data, but disclosure from improper use for answering non-authorized analytical questions occurred. This observation is also shared by other infrastructures providing research access to sensitive data, blaming a combination of enthusiasm and ignorance for attempts to bypass output checks or using data in unauthorized contexts [4].

2 Background

Specifying the technical and organizational boundaries of systems that enable governments, academia and businesses to use highly sensitive data is an ongoing field of research. Using open source tools, techniques and procedures a secure container infrastructure can be created with moderate effort given the right guidance. Practical guidelines [1] ease that process, addressing a wide range of security dimensions with and reference implementations lowering the entrance barrier for providing secure compute platform environments. It is based upon evaluation of similar infrastructure set-ups as well as the experience gathered while running a trusted third party data platform in the medical domain for almost ten years [3].

That infrastructure was set-up and operated as a joint initiative of our institutional IT operations, a security research lab as well as the data analytics team collaborating with medical experts for the semantic data management and processing. During the early days of the COVID-19 pandemic, a similar infrastructure needed to be created as part of a national advisory board within a short period of time to be able to serve a more heterogeneous group of stakeholders. Subsequently, the desire by data owners to operate such infrastructures themselves led to the development of a modular configuration with higher levels of automation in set-up and deployment.

The ePouta system [7] is another comprehensive infrastructure set-up that provides data visiting services via secured virtual machines (VMs) that host data extracts from a completely shielded central data store. Access to these VMs is provided via remote desktop software. This is similar to the reference implementation presented in this paper. However, we propose an additional layer of separation by deploying

a dedicated virtual machine accepting the remote desktop connection from which a secure shell connection needs to be established to the virtual machine hosting the actual data extract. An infrastructure similar to ePouta has been realized by DEXHELPP [11]. It also provides access to requested subsets of data via secured VMs, albeit without a remote desktop shielding the machine holding the data subsets.

Our approach is inspired by these models and follows the same core infrastructure set-up that we document at a level of detail to allow other institutions to set up a copy within their own premises. It is designed to be hosted by an external third party provider and thus needs to document and establish trust both towards the data owner as well as the external parties wanting to work with the data. But it can and will frequently be hosted by the data owner itself, thus collapsing those two roles and easing / eliminating certain process steps.

3 Project Goal

We aim at ensuring ongoing confidentiality through technical and organizational measures, integrity with our five controls, availability through deploying the system on specialized server hardware and using common tools to establish a secure connection from the open Internet, and resilience through using only best-practice open source software. In this project, we cleaned up, documented and enhanced the existing (handcrafted) infrastructure to a entirely open-source based reference implementation of a secure data infrastructure.

Data breaches are a key security issue in modern computing and have a multitude of root causes [9]. A secure system needs to deploy security controls that target every technical and organizational aspect specific to the setting of secured data visiting. We address the security of processing sensitive data by architectural design and automated decision making on behalf of stakeholders. The provider of the secure data infrastructure in legal terms acts as data processor, where the actual ingress of sensitive data is initiated by the Data Owner role (see Sec. 5.1 for detailed role definitions) as is the egress (after initiation of the Analyst). Our secure data infrastructure stores the sensitive data in a central database that has a strict firewall barrier around it. Only process-approved connections to selected VMs (from Data Owner-VMs (for data import) or to Analyst-VMs (once, on set-up, to provide an isolated copy of the data), as well as for maintenance and monitoring (Logging server) etc.) are allowed to pass this barrier.

4 Methodology

The overall concept, in a nutshell, is centered around the principle of never providing access to the central data store where all data is being held. Instead, for each individual analysis request, the data required is extracted from the central data store and copied onto a dedicated compute virtual machine

(Analyst-VM) together with the tools required to perform the analysis. Access to this Analyst-VM is granted to the (single) Analyst working on the task at hand - however, never directly, but only via a dedicated Remote Desktop-VM to introduce a media break and avoid any data flowing off via e.g. a tunnel. Thus, an Analyst can establish a remote desktop connection to a dedicated VM from which he or she has the sole possibility of establishing a secure shell connection (SSH) to the corresponding Analyst-VM, holding a copy of only the subset of data (possibly finger-printed and aggregated) as well as the tools required for addressing the task at hand. Export of any result files (trained models, figures, charts) is again possible only via a dedicated Data Owner-VM to ensure approval of Data Owner. An overview of this architecture is depicted in Figure 1 and described in further detail below. These VMs are being destroyed after a specific transfer or analysis task has been completed.

There are many data management solutions that address effective decision making in the context of preventing unintended disclosure of sensitive information. Desai et. al propose the “fives safes” dimensions [2] to maximize the usage of detailed public records while at the same time protecting personal rights of individuals. Breaking down decisions into five dimensions allows a data management solution to protect the overall confidentiality but gives enough flexibility to tailor some specific dimensions to stronger security than others. In the following, we give a short overview on the dimensions since we address them through technical enforcement and organizational processes: (i) safe projects to address management decisions regarding appropriateness of the usage of the data through auditability and review processes, (ii) safe people to identify individuals that access the sensitive data and require them to sign legally binding terms of use, (iii) safe data to ensure appropriate data de-identification and access capabilities with respect to the research questions formulated, (iv) safe settings that address the necessity of security and transparency to achieve trust with the public and data owners, (v) safe outputs to ensure only approved, aggregated research results can be exported out of the system.

To achieve a clear segmentation of data streams for different roles, we implement a control that provides strongly restricted, isolated virtual machines for any entity external to the organization. We provide a central Data Server that enables precise data identification and citation by implementing the RDA WGDC recommendations on dynamic data citation [13, 14]. The current infrastructure comes pre-configured with a PostgreSQL database, implementing the time-stamping and versioning via temporal tables [6]. It furthermore provides a query store table documenting all queries issued against the data base, including execution timestamps, result set hashes and other metadata to ensure the query results can be reproduced at any time in the future even if the data in the respective tables should change. This will allow the data used to be cited externally using a persistent identifier (currently relying on an

internal mechanism, can be replaced by a digital object identifier) that, depending on settings, can be set to re-direct to a respective landing page providing externally visible metadata information on the data subset and e.g. contact information for data access requests.

All connections to this central Data Server are one-way oriented following the recommendation on “safe data” and “safe return” for TREs [15]. Data Owner-VMs can only append data to the central Data Server during their life cycle. Analyst-VMs are configured at creation time to contain data from the central Data Server. After creation, they will never establish a connection to the central database anymore. When explicitly required from the Analyst role, there is a possibility to submit a request for data egress. Our approach is that the Analyst role places the data to be egressed in a clearly labeled export folder and the System Administrator role then transfers the data to a Data Owner-VM which is accessible by the Data Owner role. In case of approval, the data then can be re-inserted into the central database server (TRE “safe return” in terms of [15]) or exported to the Data Owner role who subsequently can make it available to anybody else. This constitutes an additional control of protecting the sensitive data. Our implementation of the secure data infrastructure requires from each virtual machine a core minimum of security controls to be present.

For Analyst-VMs (that are used by the Analyst role, see Sec. 5.1) additional policies are implemented in the secure data infrastructure. To retain all control on the VM, access is only allowed through remote desktop via a dedicated VPN Server that only allows traffic to a single Analyst-VM. This massive overhead of processes running in own VMs only allows for visual access to the data. An adversary still is able to take screenshots of e.g. paginated views of data or using code to display encoded representation of data in matrix barcodes. By having a copy of all code being deployed on VM set-up and recording both the Remote Desktop-VM data stream as well as VM activities on the Log Server allows tracing of such activities to detect unusual behavior in task processing. This is complemented by passive security measures such as data fingerprints being embedded upon VM deployment. For future work, we want to implement real-time screen watermarking as proposed in [10] to additionally be able to follow and trail back to the adversary in case of a data breach.

For the majority of the organizational measures, we require only that the analysts involved know how to use their preferred data processing and analytics tools (which are provided on-demand on the Analyst-VM). Little to no additional training thus should be required in order to execute common data science tasks on the isolated VMs. Although the secure data infrastructure is designed to automate as much of the processes as possible, a few steps require human intervention and are not suitable for automation.

5 Achievements

This section covers the improvements that have been achieved by us since the handcrafted version of the secure data infrastructure without written documentation.

5.1 Roles and Controlled Access

Physical security that restricts access to the server hardware is the first control to protect the sensitive data in the infrastructure. We recommend to place the hardware needed into a dedicated locked server rack where only a designated and certified operator can open the lock. Following the four eye principle, a key card for the server room is needed that is held solely by another operator.

Our method uses the role-based access control concept [5] where individuals are assigned a set of roles that allows them to access previously defined components in the secure data infrastructure. To prevent privilege escalation [12] attacks, we equip each role only with a bare minimum of privileges on a need-to-know principle for data access. We argue to limit the number of roles to only six in order to have a clear distinction of requirements and interests to interact with the system.

Data Owner has a strong interest in providing an untrusted expert access to the data but wants to retain control of the data and specifically reduce the risk of data leakage to an acceptable level. Our approach provides temporary and isolated Data Owner-VMs that allow import of structured data to the database of the Data Server after which it is destroyed and consigning the Data Owner full control over who the data is provided to. It furthermore has access to comprehensive logging information providing a full audit trail of all interactions with their data within the infrastructure from data import, via any provisioning steps to data deletion.

Analyst has a clear understanding on what data is required and what research questions need to be answered with it. This role can be assigned to experts that need to analyze or process the data, but where sharing the data is not feasible. With the permission of the Data Owner role, the Analyst role is able to use an according subset of the data in isolated VMs that have compute-optimized hardware configurations. Access is only granted for a limited time period with the possibility to extend it following request and approval processes via the Data Owner. The Analyst role is granted access only to their corresponding Analyst-VMs (via Remote Desktop-VMs) created explicitly for the approved set of analysis or processing goals. It is therefore possible for the Analyst role to have access to more than one VM depending on the number of independent tasks.

Data Provider is processing the data on behalf of the Data Owner. It manages the services and takes care of all

operations of creating the respective isolated VMs for Data Owner- and Analyst roles, monitors user interactions, and handles the legal contracts required. It may outsource the actual hardware provisioning to a sub-contracted Carrier role, although frequently these two roles will be combined to reduce complexity and risks. In many cases, the Data Owner may itself decide to provide the services, leading to a simpler set-up and accordingly simpler processes for data ingress by combining the Data Owner- and Data Provider roles.

Carrier is the organization that operates the secure data infrastructure. Our approach allows for the Data Provider roles to decide where the infrastructure is going to be hosted. Although we highly recommend to host it on-premise in the immediate physical control of the Data Provider, it can be deployed on a third party private cloud provider acting as a Carrier. However, the possibility of a backdoor may outweigh the benefits of predictable infrastructure costs and automated backups among others for small organizations.

Database Administrator is a role that is responsible for maintaining the central Data Server and the PostgreSQL database running on it. The Database Administrator role is nominated by the provider organization and is mutually exclusive with the System Administrator role. This exclusivity is required to not enable a change in the central Data Server and subsequently manipulate the logs in the Logging Server. With the introduction of zero-knowledge databases, this role can be made obsolete since the provider organization or Database Administrator cannot access the database anymore. This role also has to maintain the Key Servers that store the compound passphrase for decrypting the encryption key for the VM disks.

System Administrator maintains the secure data infrastructure environment, except for the central Data Server. This role also manages the platform where the infrastructure is hosted.

5.2 Isolated Virtual Machines

A virtual machine is orchestrated by a hypervisor (or “virtual machine monitor”), which has to be installed on the host either directly or on top of another operating system. The hypervisor isolates VMs from each other at all times [8]. In our case, we want to extend this isolation to a degree that artificially air-gaps each VM where only the responsible role and the secure data infrastructure itself can operate the machine within a limited boundary. However, this task is not trivial since not all approaches are equal in effectiveness. For example, the remote frame buffer protocol allows to remotely

control another machine by transmitting controlling signals like mouse- and keyboard events.

We define a set of VMs that form the core infrastructure (e.g. VPN-VMs, Data Owner-VMs, Remote Desktop VMs, Analyst-VMs, and others, cf. Sec. 5.3) on a single Virtualization Host. By only providing remote desktop capabilities via a Remote Desktop-VM, custom policies like prevention of copy and paste can be enforced with low effort but come at a cost of maintaining a secure connection to the virtual network computing (VNC) Server. It handles the requests from the VNC Client. We deploy a fresh Remote Desktop-VM (running the VNC server) for each Analyst-VM, they form a functional tuple. We encrypt the data stream using AES with keys of 128 bit length. A compromise of this key or the cipher can have fatal outcomes for our system, therefore we further isolate the remote desktop data stream using virtual private network (VPN) capabilities that creates a second encryption hull with different cipher.

5.3 Core Infrastructure Components

The Virtualization Host is the physical hardware computing unit that provides the necessary resources for the virtualized components, specifically the five core infrastructure VMs plus dedicated, temporary VMs for data delivery by Data Owners and checking safe returns or result exports, and both a Remote Desktop-VM and Analyst-VM combination temporarily per task per Analyst. It is generally recommended to use specialized server hardware for this, but the set-up works with commodity hardware as well as long as the physical specifications support the required core infrastructure VMs, as well as the two Key Servers, as depicted in Figure 1:

VPN Server is virtualized on the Virtualization Host and is the endpoint for the Analyst and Data Owner to be able to establish a connection to the secure data infrastructure. We run an IPsec/L2TP VPN server that is installed automatically by an Ansible set-up script. This component needs to be configured with a custom pre-shared-key before running the set-up playbook.

Gate Server is the virtualized firewall component that manages the traffic between the different subnets on the Virtualization Host. The service allows to filter packets based on chains. To the basic three chains (INPUT, FORWARD, OUTPUT) we only add five additional chains during the initial set-up, that group the firewall rules for the secure data infrastructure.

Data Server is the virtualized central storage that holds sensitive data and can be isolated to a level that only a System Administrator role is able to access the server for maintenance, but not to make changes to the PostgreSQL database server running on it. The PostgreSQL database implements the RDA recommendations for dynamic data citation via temporal tables.

Figure 1: The multiple security layers in our architecture. Green components handle Owner and Analyst roles, red components are restricted firewall barriers. Everything below the Provider network is virtualized on our dedicated Virtualization Host.

Installer is a virtualized component that offers a service to manage Data Owner-VMs and Analyst-VMs using Ansible playbooks. It is the only component that can do that. The mapping of users to VMs is currently implemented locally through comma-separated value files. The files also store part of the account details like e-mail addresses

and phone number for notification purposes.

Logging Server is virtualized and runs the `rsyslog` endpoint which stores all events that are occurring in the secure data infrastructure. All monitoring activity is collected here and saved in audit trails. This component should (ideally) operate using a hardware-protected write-once storage system, and have a separated access control, but is virtualized in the reference implementation set-up to provide a self-contained starting point.

Data Owner-VMs are temporary VMs created for the submission of data (ingress) by a Data Owner into the trusted infrastructure. Upon completion of the upload the data is shifted to the Data Server after which this VM can be deleted. Alternatively it may be used for “safe returns” (in terms of TREs [15]) and data- or result exports as both processes may require clearing from the Data Owner.

Analyst-VMs are temporary VMs created individually for each analysis or data processing task. Upon creation with a zero-ed storage region they are equipped with a copy of the data subset and the tools required by the Analyst. Connections are solely possible to the corresponding Remote Desktop-VM and to verified license servers when required by specific tools, as well as for transferring result data to the associated Data Owner-VM for safe return and export.

Remote Desktop-VMs are temporary VMs created individually for each Analyst-VM. We use TigerVNC as software implementation that runs inside the Remote Desktop-VM as a process.

Key Servers are two separate physical servers that each hold a part of the virtual storage encryption passphrase.

5.4 Data Ingress

Whenever a Data Owner role wants to import data into the secure data infrastructure, the data ingress process is started. Initially, he or she must sign an agreement on data delivery (“data processing agreement”) manually and provide meta data of the data set: (i) list of attributes with respective description and primary key (ii) number of records e.g. rows (iii) disclosure of format. Currently only comma-separated values are supported, providing the separator qualifier, null value encoding, boolean value encoding, date encoding and (iv) short description of the data. The Data Owner role subsequently has to request an account after signing the data processing agreement. Along with the required tools to ingress data into the system, the Data Owner role needs to disclose personal information like: (i) first- and lastname (ii) e-mail address and (iii) mobile phone number to send messages at the end of the process to. This step requires manual interaction (will

usually be automated using trusted authentication services) and currently takes currently a few minutes upon approval before the Data Owner role can access its VM. The secure data infrastructure then automatically creates a new isolated Data Owner-VM, updates the firewall rules to grant access to this machine for the Data Owner role and sends the credentials to access it and transfer the sensitive data. After confirmation that the data is completely sent (or after a pre-defined timeout of 100 days) the infrastructure locks the virtual machine, transfers the data from it and securely destroys it. The Data Owner role then is notified using two different channels that the transfer was successful.

5.5 Data Access

To access the data, an Analyst role needs to send a request to the Data Owner containing: (1) personal data that allows identification of the Analyst role; (2) required data (usually a subset of the available data); (3) task and research questions that should be answered with the required data; and (4) required tools to analyze the data and optionally prepare the data in a way that it can be re-imported into the central data store (safe return in terms of TREs [15]).

After manual check of the identity, the Data Owner role reviews the research questions and grants or rejects permission to use the data. When granted, the “data access agreement” between Data Owner role and Analyst role must be accepted. Subsequently, a request for an account along with required information: (i) first and last name, (ii) e-mail address and (iii) mobile phone number to send messages are issued.

The Data Provider then automatically provisions the Analyst role with account data to access the conditions of use. It is required from the Analyst role to accept the conditions of use containing: (1) prohibition of data download (2) prohibition of de-anonymization (3) non-disclosure agreement and (4) agreement to extensive monitoring

Subsequently, a Analyst-VM is automatically created with a pre-specified life-time (expiry date) according to the envisaged project duration (with explicit prolongation confirmation required after pre-specified maximum duration period). The requested subset of data at specific aggregation level is extracted from the central Data Server and pushed onto the Analyst-VM together with the requested (and cleared) set of tools for analysis. As the central Data Server implements the RDA WGDC [13, 14] recommendations on dynamic data citation, the respective query used to select the subset of data is stored in a query-store table with the query execution timestamp and some associated metadata. If the respective subset has to be re-created at a later point in time, the time-stamped query can be re-executed against the time-stamped and versioned database to extract the exact same subset of data, ensuring full reproducibility.

Furthermore, a dedicated Remote Desktop-VM is created to provide the sole access to the Analyst-VM. Also, the firewall

configurations are adapted to allow access by the specified user (Analyst role) to the respective Remote Desktop-VM. The Analyst role then can analyze the data as long as the timeout is not reached (by default at 100 days). Additionally, the Data Owner role has the right to lock access to the Analyst-VM any time to protect the data, and to inspect all activity happening on the Analyst-VM by inspecting its logs.

At the end of the analysis, the Analyst role may wish to re-import the data back to the secure Data Server or to export certain result files to an external machine. Depending on the approval of the Data Owner role, this is possible in our secure data infrastructure through the Data Owner-VM similar to the data ingress process in Sec. 5.4, inspection of the data to be exported or re-imported to the central Data Server, and providing an according clearance. When the safe export or re-import of data back to the central data store was granted by the Data Owner role, the Data Owner role is notified of the successful import/export and the Analyst-VM and Remote Desktop-VM is destroyed, the respective firewall entries are removed, and the access permissions revoked.

6 Conclusion

We have presented an architecture and processes for operating a secure data infrastructure that supports secure data visiting. Data Owners can make their data accessible to untrusted visitors (experts, analysts) for specific tasks while maintaining full control of how their data is being used and preventing data leakage. The concept is based on providing access to the subsets of (potentially fingerprinted and/or anonymized) data required for a specific activity via isolated virtual machines that are monitored and accessible only via remote desktop access. We implement this through well-defined processes for data provisioning, safe computing, -returns and -outputs as well as according contractual regulations.

Furthermore we presented a reference implementation of this infrastructure that is based entirely on well-studied open-source components. The set-up, configuration and core operational processes have been automated to a degree such that it can be easily deployed within a short period of time on any on-promise infrastructure or private cloud. The current version of the reference implementation covers all core components to operate it. An additional stream of research is currently investigating the bandwidth and thus amount of data theft possible via covert channels such as using time-based encoding schemes for data transmissions via flickering, or visual encodings such as barcodes. There is a strong need for solid, continuous analysis of the monitoring information, both on the visual video stream as well as the structured log files to raise according alarms and automatically trigger suitable actions to reduce the risk of data leakage.

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Availability

The entire source code of the system configuration and set-up scripts as well as the comprehensive documentation are available in the public GitLab repository [16].

References

- [1] Madhu Akula. Defenders’ guide to container infrastructure security. In Proceedings of the 26th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, page 2706–2714, Portland, OR, October 2019. USENIX Association.
- [2] Tanvi Desai, Felix Ritchie, and Richard Welpton. Five safes: Designing data access for research, 2016.
- [3] DEXHELPP. Open Source Secure Data Infrastructure and Processes. [Online; accessed March 3rd, 2021]. URL: <http://dexhelfp.at/>, 2021.
- [4] Ruben Dood. Remote access to official microdata. Presentation at 8th Conference for Social and Economic Data (KSWD), March 2020.
- [5] David Ferraiolo and Richard Kuhn. Role-Based Access Controls. In Proceedings of the 15th National Computer Security Conference, pages 554–563, October 1992.
- [6] Krishna Kulkarni and Jan-Eike Michels. Temporal Features in SQL:2011. 41(3):34–43, October 2012.
- [7] Jaakko Leinonen. ePouta Secure Cloud Service. In Sensitive Data Workshop at NeIC 2017, Umea, Sweden, May 2017.
- [8] M. Mishra, A. Das, P. Kulkarni, and A. Sahoo. Dynamic resource management using virtual machine migrations. IEEE Communications Magazine, 50(9):34–40, 2012.
- [9] A. Mousa, M. Karabatak, and T. Mustafa. Database security threats and challenges. In 2020 8th International Symposium on Digital Forensics and Security (ISDFS), pages 1–5, 2020.
- [10] Maciej Piec and Andreas Rauber. Real-time screen watermarking using overlaying layer. In 2014 Ninth International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security, pages 561–570, 2014.

- [11] Niki Popper, Florian Endel, Rudolf Mayer, Martin Bicher, and Barbara Glock. Planning future health: Developing big data and system modelling pipelines for health system research. Simulation Notes Europe, 27:203–208, 2017.
- [12] Niels Provos, Markus Friedl, and Peter Honeyman. Preventing Privilege Escalation. In Proceedings of the 12th USENIX Security Symposium, pages 231–241, August 2003.
- [13] Andreas Rauber, Ari Asmi, Dieter van Uytvanck, and Stefan Proell. Data Citation of Evolving Data: Recommendations of the Working Group on Data Citation (WGDC). <http://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00016>, October 2015.
- [14] Andreas Rauber, Ari Asmi, Dieter van Uytvanck, and Stefan Proell. Identification of Reproducible Subsets for Data Citation, Sharing and Re-Use. Bulletin of the IEEE Technical Committee on Digital Libraries (TCDL), 12(1), May 2016.
- [15] United Kingdom Health Data Research Alliance. Trusted Research Environments. July 2020. [Online]. URL: <https://ukhealthdata.org/projects/aligning-approach-to-trusted-research-environments/>. Accessed September 2020. Version 2.0.
- [16] Martin Weise. Open Source Secure Data Infrastructure and Processes. [Online; accessed January 26th, 2021]. URL: <https://gitlab.tuwien.ac.at/martin.weise/ossdip>, 2020.